

ADVERSITY INTELLIGENCE AS A CONTRIBUTING FACTOR OF TUTOR'S PERFORMANCE

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Abstract:

This paper discusses adversity intelligence, tutor's performance, and the contribution of adversity intelligence towards the performance of tutor in Learning Activity Center (SKB). The discussion in this paper is presented based on the research findings, where the research was done by using correlation research design and all tutors in Learning Activity Center of West Sumatra as the population. From the discussion, it can be concluded that there were many tutors in Learning Activity Center of West Sumatra whose adversity intelligence and performance were still low and the adversity intelligence had a significant contribution towards tutors' performance.

Keywords: adversity, intelligence, tutor, performance

1. Introduction

Tutor is an important element in the Learning Activity Center/ Non-formal Education Units (Latchem, 2014) (Ngaka, Openjuru, & Mazur, 2012) (Witthaus et al., 2016). The success of a tutor can be seen through his performance (Affeldt, Weitz, Siol, Markic, & Eilks, 2015). This performance becomes an urgent in an institution, as without any performance then the goal of the institution cannot be achieved as expected (Witthaus et al., 2016). *"Performance or work performance is the execution of functions demanded from a person, it is an act, an achievement, a general exhibition of skills"* (Whitmore, 1997). Unfortunately, there are still many tutors who have not performed in accordance with

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the performance expected. The factors affect performance are individual characteristics, organizational characteristics, and work characteristics (Kopelman, 1988). One of the individual characteristic factors affecting performance is Adversity Intelligence (Effendi, Mohd, Khairani, & Razak, 2015) (Song & Woo, 2015) (Verma, Aggarwal, & Bansal, 2017).

Based on the background of the problem as proposed above, the purposes of this paper are to see: (1) An overview of the adversity intelligence of tutors in Learning Activity Center, (2) An overview of the performance of tutors in Learning Activity Center, (3) Whether there is a correlation between the adversity intelligence and performance of tutors in Learning Activity Center, and (4) How much the correlation between adversity intelligence towards tutors' performance in Learning Activity Center is.

2. Material and Methods

This study was designed by using correlational research design. The correlational design both explains the description of the actual phenomena of the variables studied and reveals the presence or absence of the correlation between the independent variables (predictors) of adversity intelligence (X) and the dependent variable (criterion), i.e. performance of tutors (Y), and find the contribution of independent variable to the dependent one.

The population of this study was all tutors in learning activity center in West Sumatra. In order to select the samples, stratified random sampling technique was used. Stratified random sampling can be used if the population is heterogeneous, and the heterogeneity has a significant meaning on the achievement of the research objectives, the researcher can take the sample in this way. In this case, the tutors learn to have the heterogeneity of tutor strata, namely tutors First Learning, and tutors Madya Learning (Regulation of the State Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform number 15 year 2010).

Instrument used to collect the data on Adversity Intelligence (X) and tutors' Performance (Y) was Likert scale measurement scale with scale 4, and four alternative answers: Strongly Agree (SS), Agree (S), Disagree (TS), and Strongly Disagree (STS). To measure the accuracy and reliability of the instrument used in this study, a test or a try-out had been conducted on the tutors who were not selected as the research samples. The results of this try-out then were analyzed by using validity and reliability test. The validity was measured by conducting a try-out test on the subjects of the research who were not selected as the samples. The results were analyzed empirically by correlating the grain and total score by using the Pearson Product Moment correlation technique.

Besides, reliability was measured by using items consistency test, which is the consistency of the respondent's answer on an item in Alpha coefficient.

If the Alpha coefficient shows ≥ 0.70 , then it can be said that the items in the questionnaire are reliable. The analysis technique used in this study was simple regression technique. It is an analytical technique used to analyze the correlation and see the magnitude of one dependent variable and one independent variable. Therefore, a computer assistance, that was Statistic Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) for Window Release 17.0 was used.

3. Results and Discussion

a. Results

1) An Overview of the Adversity Intelligence of Tutors in Learning Activity Center in West Sumatra

Based on the results of data analysis, which was conducted by using the percentage, the performance can be seen in table 1.

Table 1: The Adversity Intelligence of Tutors in Learning Activity Center in Padang City

Score Interval	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
36-58	Very High	8	21
43-55	High	9	24
30-42	Low	13	34
16-29	Very Low	8	21
Total		38	100

Table 1 illustrates that there were many tutors in learning activity center in West Sumatra whose adversity intelligence was still low. The highest frequency (13) was in 30-42 score interval, with low category. It means that from 38 tutors 13 (34%) got the score between 30-42, where the category was low. Further details about the overview can be seen in the following histogram.

Figure 1: Tutors' Intelligence Adversity Histogram

2) An Overview of the Performance of Tutors in Learning Activity Center in West Sumatra

Based on the results of data analysis, which was conducted by using the percentage, the performance can be seen in table 2.

Table 2: The Performance of Tutors in Learning Activity Center in West Sumatra

Score Interval	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
65-80	Very High	7	18
50-64	High	11	29
35-49	Low	12	32
20-34	Very Low	8	21
Total		38	100

Table 2 shows that the level of performance of many tutors in learning activity center in West Sumatra was still low. The findings show that 12 tutors had score between 35-49, which was categorized as low. In other words, 12 of 38 tutors (32%) got score on a range of interval scores 35-49 (which was included in the low category). The following Histogram illustrates further details.

Figure 2: Performance of Tutors in Learning Activity Center of Padang City Histogram

b. Discussions

In this section, before data analysis was conducted, the hypothesis result of simple regression requirements (simple regression) was presented.

1) Hypothesis Test of Simple Regression Requirements

Before analyzing the data by using simple regression analysis technique, a hypothesis test was used as the requirement in simple regression analysis technique. According to Sudarmanto (2005), the tests are normality, linearity, homogeneity, multicollinearity, autocorrelation, and heteroscedasticity test. Each test is described as follows.

The normality test is conducted to determine whether the distribution of the data follows or approaches the normal distribution as good data is data that has a normal distribution pattern or close to normal. Based on the normality test, viewed from the distribution of data on the QQ plot then the data was clustered on the test line and leads to the top right. Accordingly, a reasonable regression is used to analyze the data.

The homogeneity tests are conducted to detect the presence or absence of homogeneity, used to see the spread of points on the graph. If the points spread and do not form a certain pattern, it means that the data is homogeneous (Santoso, 2004). When it is viewed from the graph and random points are found, it can be concluded that the distribution of data homogeneous. Thus, the analysis is worth continuing.

The linearity test is done in pairs between each independent variable with the dependent one. In this case, the linearity of the correlation between independent variable, achievement motivation, and dependent variable, work readiness, will be seen. The linearity test is performed using compare means analysis by comparing the significance value with the selected alpha level (here 5%). The data is said to be linear because it is significant for the deviation from linearity > of the specified alpha. Based on the results of data analysis of the scatter plot, the regression line on the graph of each variable pointing to the top right. In other words, the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variable is linear. Therefore, regression analysis can be used.

2) Correlation between Adversity Intelligence and Tutor's Performance

The first hypothesis is formulated in the form of a working hypothesis (H_a) which says, "There is a significant correlation between adversity intelligence and tutor's performance in learning activities center in West Sumatra." This hypothesis was tested by using Pearson correlation (r). The results of correlation analysis (r) obtained was 0.854 with a significant level of 0.000 or smaller than the tolerance given 0.05. Based on the results, the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected. It can be said that adversity intelligence has a significant correlation with the performance of tutors. It means that if the tutor's adversity intelligence is improved, it will be followed by the increased of tutor's performance or vice versa. It is illustrated in the following table.

Table 3: Summary of Independent Variable Coefficient Correlation with Dependent Variables

Variable	Coefficient Correlation (R)	Probability	Note
X → Y	0,854	0,000	Significant Correlation

Notes:

(X) = Work Readiness

(Y) = Performance

3) Contribution of Job Satisfaction towards Tutor's Performance

Contribution of adversity intelligence (X) to work performance (Y). The contribution of independent variable of job satisfaction (X) to tutor's performance (Y) will be seen from the value of R Square in Summary Model table. R Square value was used to test the amount of contribution. By using the Summary Model table, it was found that the magnitude of R Square was 0.725 with significance 0.000. It means that the variable of adversity intelligence (X) gives a significant contribution of 0,729 (72.9%) on the performance of the tutors (Y).

Summary^b Model

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.854 ^a	.729	.721	8.43285

a. Predictors: (Constant), K.Advsty

b. Dependent Variable: Performance

4) Coefficient Test of Regression Equation

The coefficient test of regression equation can be seen on the regression analysis as being shown in table 5. Table 5 shows that the test table of regression coefficient of constant is 3,975 coefficient of Adversity Intelligence (X) 0.907. Therefore, the model of regression equation is $Y = 3,975 + 0,907 X$. Further details can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5: Coefficient Test Results of Regression Equation

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.837	4.883		.376	.709
	K.Advsty	1.086	.110	.854	9.832	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.975	4.634		.858	.397
	K.Kerja	.907	.091	.856	9.920	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

a. Conclusions

Based on the results of research and discussion, there are some conclusions that can be drawn, as follows.

- 1) Adversity intelligence of many tutors in Learning Activity Center (SKB) in West Sumatra is still in the low category. The low level of adversity intelligence can be seen from the results of this research that show many tutors who cannot calmly face the difficulties of tasks assigned to them, many feel resigned because they feel unable to keep up with the progress of their peers, and still consider if there is a mistake in performing their tasks due to being disturbed by their peers.
- 2) The performance level of many tutors in Learning Activity Center in West Sumatra is still in the low category. Their low performance can be concluded from the research results that show that many tutors do not perform their tasks on time. Besides, they have no initiative in solving difficult tasks, and often feel that the tasks given are too difficult.
- 3) Adversity intelligence has a significant correlation with the performance of tutors in Learning Activity Center. It means that if the adversity intelligence is improved, the tutor's performance will be increased or vice versa.
- 4) Adversity intelligence has a significant contribution to the performance of tutor in learning activities center. In other words, the increase or decrease of the tutor's performance can be seen from the increase or decrease of the adversity intelligence. Therefore, in order to improve a tutor's performance, the first thing that have to be done is improving his adversity intelligence.

b. Recommendations

Following up the research findings that illustrate that the low level of adversity intelligence that contribute significantly to the low performance of the tutors in learning activity center, it is suggested that the leaders of institutions, tutors coordinator, authorized officials, and academic staff can provide input and guidance to improve tutors' adversity intelligence such as improving positive competitiveness in work, increasing motivation, and providing learning opportunities.

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